

THE EFFECT OF PROCESSING PARAMETERS ON STRUCTURAL PROPERTY FOR FILAMENT-WOUND COMPOSITE PRESSURE VESSELS

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1 Introduction

Filament winding is a popular production technique for composite structures. Cylinder pressure vessel with elliptical dome is an efficient product which can make full use of tensile strength of fiber. To achieve the most efficient use of the reinforcement material the fiber should be placed in the maximum load directions or in geodesic path. This is not always achievable as the fibers must not slip during the winding process due to windability. Windability means fiber bands should cover uniformly on the mandrel without voids or significant overlap toward radial and circumferential directions. Realistic pattern information is very important for an optimal design because it is directly related with the accuracy if finite element analyses.

F.H.Abdalla[1] design a lathe-type machine for low cost filament winding process. Haisheng Li[2] presents a new class of trajectories with more freedom by generalizing spline and give the conditions to make these splines on cylinders and cones stable. Cheol[4] use semi-geodesic path algorithm to calculate possible winding patterns taking into account the windability and slippage between the fiber and the mandrel surface. D.T.Jones[5] describes delta-axisymmetric methods that result in a constant thickness lay-up of composite over the end closures of a dome-end cylindrical vessel. Tae-kyung[6] verified the size effect on the fiber strength of a composite pressure vessel but didn't mention the winding pattern.

In this paper, the practical process parameters which are important for design are studied and

two methods for calculating mandrel rotated angle are discussed.

2 Theory for filament winding trajectories

2.1 Plane-hypothesis theory

This is a simplified method that supposes the fiber path at dome lies in a plane. It is easy to calculate the mandrel rotating angle at dome as following:

$$\theta_1 = 2 \left(90 + \sin^{-1} \frac{2htg\alpha - d}{D} \right)$$

A series of two consecutive fiber paths is called a winding circuit. The first fiber path crosses the mandrel from one end to the other end, and the second fiber path returns to the first end. The mandrel rotating angle during a winding circuit followed:

$$\theta_n = \frac{L \cdot tg\alpha}{\pi D} \cdot 360 + 2 \left(90 + \sin^{-1} \frac{2htg\alpha - d}{D} \right)$$

where L is length of cylinder, α is winding angle, D is diameter of cylinder, d is diameter of polar opening. H is the height of the dome.

Fig.1 fiber path for plane-hypothesis

2.2 Geodesic theory

According to differential geometry of generalized

Fig.2. parameter figure for ellipse equation

spaces, a regular three-dimensional surface can be described as a vector function of two independent parameters:

$$S(\theta, \phi) = \{x(\theta, \phi), y(\theta, \phi), z(\theta, \phi)\} \text{ with } \theta, \phi \in \mathcal{R}$$

For ellipsoid shape of mandrel dome, its surface can be described as following:

$$r = \{b \cos u \cos v, b \cos u \sin v, a \sin u\}$$

Coefficients of the first fundamental form are equal to:

$$E = \left(\frac{\partial x}{\partial u}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial u}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial u}\right)^2 = b^2 \sin^2 u + a^2 \cos^2 u$$

$$F = \frac{\partial x}{\partial u} \cdot \frac{\partial x}{\partial v} + \frac{\partial y}{\partial u} \cdot \frac{\partial y}{\partial v} + \frac{\partial z}{\partial u} \cdot \frac{\partial z}{\partial v} = 0$$

$$G = \left(\frac{\partial x}{\partial v}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial v}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial v}\right)^2 = b^2 \cos^2 u$$

Differential equation of geodesic line at revolutionary curved surface is:

$$\frac{\partial \tau}{\partial u} = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{E}{G}} \frac{\partial nE}{\partial v} - \frac{\partial nG}{\partial u} \text{tg} \tau = \text{tg} u \cdot \text{tg} \tau$$

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial u} = \sqrt{\frac{E}{G}} \text{tg} \tau = \frac{\sqrt{\sin^2 u + k^2 \cos u}}{\cos u} \text{tg} \tau \quad (2)$$

Where τ is winding angle and v is mandrel rotating angle.

3. Windability and practical wind pattern

As mentioned above, windability is very important because some of the patterns calculated by Eq.(1) and Eq.(2) may be useless for the manufacture of filament wound structures unless uniform coverage is considered. If the number of fiber bands in a layer is N and the circumferential shifted integer is K , the

relationship of K and N should be relative prime in order to satisfy the windability.

Practical mandrel rotating angle is equal to:

$$\theta_n = \frac{K}{N} \cdot 360 + \frac{b}{N\pi D \cos \alpha} \cdot 360 \quad (3)$$

Where b is width of fiber band. Data for relationship between mandrel rotating angle and number of fiber bands showed in table-1.

Table-1 relationship between mandrel rotating angle and number of fiber bands

bands	Patten K/N	Angle °	Patten K/N	Angle °	Patten K/N	Angle °
1	1/1	360	2/1	720	3/1	1080
2	1/2	180	3/2	540	5/2	900
3	1/3	120	4/3	480	7/3	840
	2/3	240	5/3	600	8/3	960
4	1/4	90	5/4	450	9/4	810
	3/4	270	7/4	630	11/4	990
5	1/5	72	6/5	432	11/5	792
	2/5	144	7/5	504	12/5	864
	3/5	216	8/5	576	13/5	936
	4/5	288	9/5	648	14/5	1008
6	1/6	60	7/6	420	13/6	780
	5/6	300	11/6	660	17/6	1020

Winding pattern for different number of fiber bands is showed in fig.-3.

(1) N=3 (2) N=4 (3) N=5 (4) N=6

Fig.-3 Winding pattern for different number of fiber bands

According to equation (1) or (2), mandrel rotating angle can be calculated. The nearest winding pattern can be found in table-1. spatial trajectories was adjusted slightly to be identical with the practical winding pattern. The following winding angle at dome of arbitrary position can be obtained:

$$\alpha = \arcsin \frac{\frac{\Delta \theta}{360} \cdot \pi D}{\sqrt{(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2}} \quad (4)$$

Thickness at dome is equal to:

$$t_f = \frac{D \cos \alpha_0}{d \cos \alpha} t_{fa} \quad (5)$$

Where d is diameter at dome of arbitrary position, t_{fa} is thickness of cylinder.

4. Result and discussion

The performance of composite structures completely depends on the distribution of the fiber, which is determined by the filament winding pattern.

3-D spatial data of the winding trajectories were simulated by using C++ programming language. The parameters were showed in fig.4.

Fig.-4 Winding trajectories simulation

For example, $L=410\text{mm}$, $D=146\text{mm}$, $h=40\text{mm}$, $d=31.5\text{mm}$, $p=0.55$. mandrel winding angle according to equation(1) is 502° , 504° should be chosen according to table-1. It is 442.7° according to equation(2) and 450° is the nearest angle for windability.

442.7° is the most stable pattern at dome due to it is geodesic line and 450° is the nearest angle to geodesic trajectories meanwhile it keeps to windability. Comparatively, the winding pattern according to plane-hypothesis is farther to the geodesic line and unstable though it is applied widely because it is simple and easy to be used. The thickness was calculated according to equation (5). The results showed that nearly no difference between the result of two method. However, this was not the real truth because the fiber would slide toward stable trajectories when it was far from the geodesic line. The result was that the thickness near polar hole was bigger than anticipated due to the bigger mandrel rotating angle.

Fig.-5 Winding angle for different methods

The thickness was related with the friction coefficient between fiber band and mandrel. Therefore, the fiber path should be close to the geodesic line to avoid fiber stack and sliding. The result for different parameters showed in Fig.-7.

Fig.-7 mandrel rotating angle at different parameters

For $L=500\text{mm}$, $p=0.5$, radius of cylinder R and radius of polar opening r_0 is variable. The result showed that the mandrel winding angle decreased as radius of cylinder increase and radius of polar opening decrease. The difference between result of two methods increases as r_0 increase, but it is nearly constant when R increased.

5. Conclusion

In this research, winding patterns considering windability were presented. Two methods for calculating mandrel rotating angle were discussed. Plane-hypothesis method gave the unstable winding trajectories far from the geodesic line and result in fiber stack especially

when radius of polar opening increased. The angle at dome have no obvious difference with two methods but the thickness calculated by plane-hypothesis near polar opening increased due to unstable path and fiber stack. Plane-hypothesis method was suggested not to be applied during fiber winding process though it is simple and easy to be used.

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